

Model the Reservoir Fluid Behavior and Pressure Maintenance Through Gas Cycling in Gas Condensate Reservoir

ISSN (e) 2520-7393
 ISSN (p) 2521-5027
 Received on 08, Sept-2018
 Revised on 02-Oct-2018
 www.estirj.com

Noshad Shar¹, Dr. Sarfraz Ahmed Jokhio², Naeem Ul. Hussain Dahraj³, Dr. Abdul Haque Tunio⁴, Habib Rehman Solangi⁵

^{1,2,4}Institute of Petroleum & Natural Gas Engineering, Mehran University of Engineering and Technology Jamshoro, Pakistan.

³Senior Reservoir Engineer, Pakistan Petroleum Limited (PPL).

⁵Trainee Production Engineer, Oil and Gas Development Company Limited (OGDCL)..

Abstract: Compositional reservoirs (gas-condensate) have complex behaviour. Gas-condensate reservoirs are critical reservoirs in nature. Gas-condensate reservoir has single phase fluid above the dew-point pressure and below the dew-point pressure has two-phase fluids. In depletion method, reservoir pressure decreases below the dew-point pressure at that pressure two phase-fluid start to form gas and condensate in the reservoir and liquid accumulate around the wellbore that is condensate banking. The accumulation of condensate around the wellbore that blocks the perforated channels and decreases the flow of gas and also the valuable condensate. It is necessary to model the reservoir fluid behaviour before the production. The EOS “Peng Robinson” is the best equation to model the reservoir fluid behaviour for compositional reservoirs. Lab data CCE, CVD and Separator must have matched with the EOS by using PVT software with ± 5 acceptable error. Eclipse E-300 is the best software to simulate the compositional reservoir. Condensate can be re-vaporizing into the single-phase fluid by re-injecting (gas cycling) the gas into the reservoir to maintain the reservoir pressure above the dew point pressure. Gas cycling can maintain the reservoir pressure by two methods 1st Partial pressure maintenance method and 2nd Full pressure maintenance method. Select the best one recovery method depletion, partial pressure maintenance or full pressure maintenance. Select the best production and injection layers (perforation depth), the number of wells, well patterns, production and injection rates and gas cycling years. And select the best cases of a maximum value of NPV and IRR by using the petroleum policy 2012.

Keywords Gas cycling; Gas Condensate.; Gas cycling; Slip; Wheel-Rail Dynamics

1. Introduction

Gas-condensate reservoir is defined as the reservoir temperature is between the critical temperature and cricondentherm. Critical point is that point where all the intensive properties of the fluid are same and above the critical temperature, gas cannot be formed. And cricondentherm point is that point where both fluids are co-existing. Above the cricondentherm temperature, further fluid cannot be a form (Tarek Ahmed).

Gas-condensate reservoirs have complex behavior by decreasing the reservoir pressure below the dew point pressure. Condensate start to form in the reservoir below the dew-point pressure. The accumulation of condensate near the wellbore causes to decrease the remaining production of gas and valuable condensate and is named as condensate banking. Condensate banking is formed around the wellbore and blocks the flowing channels and perforations Figure 1.

The condensate banking decreases the remaining gas flow rate and rate of remaining valuable condensate. Before the production or injection, it is necessary to model the reservoir fluid behavior. Modelling of reservoir fluid behavior means

to validate the lab data by comparing (history matching) with the EOS (Peng Robinson). Lab data which has obtained by CCE, CVD experiments that data is matching with the numerical results (EOS). Lab data is not completely valid, in some cases it has errors. These errors can be rectified by history matching. It is must be matched the dew-point, the slope of the line from the dew-point and maximum liquid dropout from the CVD data [2].

Figure 1. Condensate Banking around the Wellbore [6]

Figure 2. Decreasing of gas flow rate due to condensate banking [17].

Before the production or injection, it is necessary to model the reservoir fluid behavior. Modelling of reservoir fluid behavior means to validate the lab data by comparing (history matching) with the EOS (Peng Robinson). Lab data which has obtained by CCE, CVD experiments that data is matching with the numerical results (EOS). Lab data is not completely valid, in some cases it has errors. These errors can be rectified by history matching. It is must be matched the dew-point, the slope of the line from the dew-point and maximum liquid dropout from the CVD data [2].

Peng Robinson EOS has the best result to history match. This equation is used to improve the liquid density of the reservoir. This equation has more accurate results than other equations.

$$\left[P + \frac{a(T)}{v(v+b)+b(v-b)} \right] (V - b) = RT \quad (1)$$

2. Equation of State (Peng Robinson)

The Equation of state is the mathematical calculation by using Peng Robinson Equation. Peng Robinson Equation has best results to calculate the compositional reservoir fluid behavior and history match by using PVT software. History match is the comparison of lab and EOS results. In this paper two lab methods have used, constant composition expansion (CCE) and constant volume depletion (CVD) to history match and got best simulation results. Figure 3. Showing CCE relative volume has matched with the EOS, Figure 4. Showing CCE Z-factor has matched with EOS, Figure 5. Showing the CCE liquid dropout has matched with EOS and Figure 6. Showing the CVD liquid dropout also has matched with the EOS by using PVT software.

1. Simulation Cases

3.1 Depletion Method

For compositional reservoir Eclipse E-300 has used and got the final results of NPV, IRR, gas recovery and condensate recovery through the selection of different cases as

1. Layers
2. Well count
3. Well pattern
4. Production rate
5. Field rate (Plant limit)

The best case which has a maximum NPV 622.4 MMS\$ Figure 10. and best recovery of gas 41.42% and oil 39.35% with minimum production of water Figure 7. Case 5 is the best case in Table 1. Simulation results are showing in Table1.

Figure 3. CCE-Relative volume matched with EOS

Figure 4. CCE Z-factor (Vapor) matched with the EOS

Figure 5. CCE Liquid dropout matched with the EOS

Figure 6. CVD Liquid dropout matched with the EO

Figure 7. Recovery of Gas and Condensate with the minimum production of water by Depletion method

3.2 Partial Pressure Maintenance Method

The total (100%) amount of gas which is producing from the field that the same amount of gas re-injecting into the reservoir to maintain the reservoir pressure above the dew-point pressure to produce the maximum amount of condensate.

The recovery of gas is 85.23% and condensate has 77.73% with the minimum production of water Figure 8. and NPV is 865 MM\$ Figure 10. Case 6 is the best in Table 2. Simulation results are showing in Table 2.

Figure 8. Recovery of Gas and Condensate by Partial Pressure Method.

3.3 Full Pressure Maintenance Method

Full pressure maintenance is the pressure maintenance above the dew-point pressure. Above the dew-point pressure is the only gas phase and condensate banking cannot be formed. Full pressure maintenance is used with the gas cycling to maintain the reservoir pressure above the dew point pressure and maintain the reservoir volume. Some amount of condensate is producing with gas that condensate cannot

reinject into the reservoir and the gas is completely reinjecting into the reservoir. Now the volume of produced condensate can be maintained with the injection of foreign gas. The injection pressure 6000 psia is the best for full pressure maintenance and has the best recovery of gas 67.05% and condensate has 70.59% Figure 9. NPV has obtained 854.4 MM\$ Figure 10. 6000 psia injection pressure is the best injection pressure in Table 3. Simulation results are showing in Table 3 (Annex: -A).

Figure 9. Recovery of Gas and Condensate by Full Pressure Maintenance Method where pressure is above the dew-point pressure

2. Results

Total oil in place in the reservoir is 23.8 MMSTB and gas is 176000 MMSCF. In 1st case (Depletion) has maximum production of condensate is 3.36 MMSTB and gas is 72900

MMSCF. In this case, the number of wells is 4 where two wells were drilled in 2009 and production has started in 2010, the 3rd well has drilled in 2011 and 4th well has drilled in 2012. 2nd case (Partial pressure maintenance) has

maximum production of oil is 18.5 MMSTB and gas is 150,000 MMSCF. There are 5 wells, 3 production wells and 2 injection wells. 2 productions and 1 injection wells were drilled in 2009, 1 production and 1 injection wells were drilled in 2010. 3rd case (Full pressure maintenance) is also the type of injection method in which foreign gas is injecting

with gas cycling. In this method, oil has produced 19MMSTB and gas has produced 158,000 MMSCF at the injection pressure 16000 psia. There are 5 wells, 3 production wells and 2 injection wells. 2 productions and 1 injection wells were drilled in 2009, 1 production and 1 injection wells were drilled in 2010.

Figure 10. NPV's of Depletion, Partial pressure maintenance and Full pressure maintenance methods.

3. Conclusion

Depletion method has a low value of NPV 622.4 MM\$ and oil recovery is 39.35% and gas recovery is 41.42%. In depletion, method recovery is low due to condensate banking. Partial pressure maintenance is the best case which has maximum NPV 865 MM\$ and recovery of oil is 77.73% and gas recovery is 85.23%. Gas cycling has prevented from the condensate banking and reservoir pressure maintained above the dew-point pressure. Full pressure maintenance has NPV 854.4 MM\$ that is less than the partial pressure maintenance method. Recovery of oil is 70.59% and gas recovery is 67.05%. No need for the full pressure maintenance.

References

- [1]. S.E. Chibueze, S.U. Ibeh, I.N. Onugha, and B. Obah, depart; "Performance Analysis of Gas Cycling Operation in Retrograde Gas Condensate Reservoir- A Niger Delta Case Study"; SPE-189135-MS; Nigeria ATCE held in Lagos Nigeria; 2017; 1-2
- [2]. Muhammad S. Abdullah, KFUPM; Makki A. Al-Zawad, KFUPM; Michael L. Fraim, KFUPM; "Common Misinterpretations of Gas Condensate Reservoirs"; SPE-187995-MS; Presented in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia ATSE in Dammam; 2017; 2-3
- [3]. S.E. Chibueze, S.U. Ibeh, I.N. Onugha, and B. Obah, depart; "Performance Analysis of Gas Cycling Operation in Retrograde Gas Condensate Reservoir- A Niger Delta Case Study"; SPE-189135-MS; Presented in Nigeria ATCE held in Lagos Nigeria; 1-2; 2017.
- [4]. Muhammad S. Abdullah, KFUPM; Makki A. Al-Zawad, KFUPM; Michael L. Fraim, KFUPM; "Common Misinterpretations of Gas Condensate Reservoirs"; SPE-187995-MS; Presented in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia ATSE in Dammam; 2-3; 2017
- [5]. A. Kumar, and M.E Gohary, ADCO; K. S Pedersen, Calsep A/S; J. Azeem, Calsep FZ LLC; "Gas Injection as an Enhanced Recovery Technique for Gas Condensates. A Comparison of three Injection Cases"; SPE-177778-MS; Presented at Abu Dhabi IPEC; 2015
- [6]. Mohammad Abdul Qadeer and Siddiqui, Dr. Sami Al Nuaim, Rizwan Ahmed Khan, KFUPM; "Well Placement and Rate Optimization for Gas Cycling in Gas Condensate Reservoirs"; SPE-172641-MS; Presented at Manama Bahrain; 2015
- [7]. Anton Y. Yushkov, and Pavel V. Merkushin, Tyumen Petroleum Research Center, Rosneft; "Evaluation of cycling scenario for Achimov formations of Urengoykoye gas-condensate field"; SPE-176582-MS; Presented at Russian Petroleum Technology Conference held in Moscow; 2015
- [8]. M. Bartolomeu, A. Abdrakhmanov*, Norwegian U. Science and Technology (*Now with Fluor Kazakhstan INC); SPE-171453-MS; Presented at Adelaide Australia; 2014
- [9]. A. Nikonov, I. Pyatov, A. Krupstev, and S. Zhukov, ROMAN CAPITAL PLC; E. Egorova, Lomonosov Moscow State University of Fine Chemical Technologies; J. Lievios and. Muravyev, Weatherford; "Development of Remote Gas Condensate Fields: Challenges and Solutions"; SPE-176660; Presented at Moscow Russia; 2015

- [10]. Gina Vega Riveros, SPE, American Land, Emad Yehya, SPE, Smoothwell for Oil Services and Luigi Saputelli, SPE; "Recovery of Retrograde Condensed Liquid in Mature Reservoirs of Gas Condensate in Latin America"; OTC 22509; Presented at Rio de Janeiro, Brazil; 2011
- [11]. S. Gerami, National Iranian Oil Co, and A. Sadeghi and M. Mashih, Sharif University of Technology; "New Technique for Calculation of Well Deliverability in Gas Condensate Reservoir"; SPE 130139; Presented at Manama, Bahrain; 2010
- [12]. Mohammad A. Sayed, Ghaithan A. Al-Muntasheri, Aramco Services Company & Aramco Research Centers-Houston, Saudi Aramco; "Liquid Bank Removal in Production Wells Drilled in Gas-condensate Reservoirs: A Critical Review"; SPE 168153; Presented at Lafayette, USA; 2014
- [13]. Otavie Imo-Jack, SPE, The Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria; "PVT Characterization of a Gas Condensate Reservoir and Investigation of factors affecting Deliverability"; SPE 140629; Presented at Tinapa-Calabar, Nigeria; 2010
- [14]. Hai X. Vo, and Roland N. Horne, Stanford University; "Experimental Study of Composition Variation During Flow of Gas-Condensate; SPE-175011-MS; Presented at Houston, Texas, USA; 2015
- [15]. Julius U. Akpabio, University of Uyo; Emmanuel E. Udofia, Michael Ogbu, The Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria; "PVT Fluid Characterization and Consistency Check for Retrograde Condensate Reservoir Modeling"; SPE-172359-MS; Presented at Logas, Nigeria; 2014
- [16]. Mohammad A.Q. Siddiqui, Dr. Sami Al-Nuaim, and Rizwan Ahmed Khan, KFUPM; "Stochastic Optimization of Gas Cycling in Gas Condensate Reservoir"; SPE-172107-MS; Presented at Abu Dhabi, UAE; 2014
- [17]. Understanding Gas-Condensate Reservoir; Schlumberger Oilfield review, 2005/2006

About Authors

Noshad Shar is the member of Society of Petroleum Engineering (SPE). He has done Bachelors of Engineering in Petroleum and Gas Engineering, Dawood University of Engineering & Technology Karachi, Pakistan (2013-2017). He is the student of Masters of Engineering at Institute of Petroleum and Natural Gas Engineering, Mehran University of Engineering & Technology Jamshoro, Pakistan. His areas of interest are Reservoir Simulation of Compositional Reservoirs, Reservoir Modeling, Production Optimization, Well Stimulation and Drilling Operations.

Dr. Sarfraz Ahmed Jokhio is the Professor at the Institute of Petroleum and Natural Gas Engineering, Mehran University of Engineering & Technology Jamshoro, Pakistan. He has done Bachelors of Engineering in Petroleum and Natural Gas Engineering, Mehran University of Engineering and Technology Jamshoro, Pakistan (1984-1989). He has completed Masters of Engineering and also the Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Petroleum Engineering from the University of Oklahoma, USA (1995-2001). He got

the job at Oklahoma University, ESP Sizing and Installing (2000- May 2002). He joined Schlumberger company as a Reservoir Engineer at Houston, Texas (2003-June2005). And he got the job at the Saudi Aramco as a Senior Reservoir Engineer, Dhahran (2005-2016). His areas of interest are Reservoir Management, Reservoir Monitoring, ESP Sizing & Performance Optimization, Water flooding, Multilateral Well Design, Well Performance Optimization, Smart Completions, Long-Term Field Development Planning and Reservoir Simulation.

Naeem Ul. Hussain Dahraj is the Senior Reservoir Engineer at Pakistan Petroleum Limited (PPL). He has done Bachelors of Engineering in Petroleum & Natural Gas Engineering, Mehran University of Engineering and Technology Jamshoro, Pakistan (2005-2008). He got a job in New Horizon Exploration & Production Limited, Karachi as Assistant Petroleum Engineer (2009-2010) and he promoted as Petroleum Engineer (2010-2012). He joined KUFPEC, Islamabad as a Petroleum Engineer (2012). He got the full bright scholarship for Masters of Science in Petroleum Engineering from the University of Oklahoma, USA (2013-2015). After completion of masters, he got the job at Pakistan Petroleum Limited (PPL) as Senior Reservoir Engineer Asset (2015-2016) and he promoted as Senior Reservoir Engineer, Reservoir Modelling (2016-present). His areas of interest are Project Planning, Field Development, Reservoir Simulation, Petroleum Economics and Product Optimization.

Dr. Abdul Haque Tunio is the Director at the Institute of Petroleum & Natural Engineering, Mehran University of Engineering & Technology Jamshoro, Pakistan. He has done Bachelors of Engineering in Petroleum & Natural Gas Engineering, Mehran University of Engineering and Technology Jamshoro, Pakistan. He has completed Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) from Mehran University of Engineering & Technology Jamshoro, Pakistan (2002-2008). His areas of interest are Enhance Oil Recovery (Miscible Gas Injection, Chemical Injection and Thermal Recovery), Pressure Transient Testing and Production Engineering.

Habib Rehman Solangi is the Trainee Production Engineer at the Oil and Gas Development Company Limited (OGDCL). He has done Bachelors of Engineering in Petroleum and Gas Engineering Dawood University of Engineering & Technology Karachi, Pakistan (2013-2017). He has presented two research papers at the Annual Technical Conference (ATC) Islamabad. His areas of Interests are Reservoir management, Pressure Transient Analysis.

Annexure-A

TABLE 1. SELECTION OF BEST CASE OF DEPLETION METHOD

Cases	No: of Wells	NPV MM\$	IRR %	Gas Produced %	Oil Produced %
1. Selected Layers	2	533.4	113	40	37.80
2. Selected of well count	4	595.8	137	41.88	39.57
3. Selected Well Pattern	4	597.4	137	42.67	40.14
4. Selected Production rate	4	613.1	167	41.65	38.92
5. Selected field rate	4	622	153	41.42	39.35

TABLE 2. SELECTION OF BEST CASE OF PARTIAL PRESSURE METHOD

Cases	Production Wells	Injection Wells	NPV MM\$	IRR %	Gas Produced %	Oil Produced %
1. Selected Layer	1	1	412	64	55	44.54
2. Selected of well count	3	2	715	115	67.05	65.13
3. Selected Well Pattern	3	2	755.8	118	68.18	71.43
4. Selected rates of Prod and Injection wells	3	2	858.7	162	76.14	74.37
5. Selected field rate	3	2	858.7	162	73.86	73.95
6. Selected cycling years	3	2	865	162	85.23	77.73

TABLE 3. SELECTION OF BEST CASE OF FULL PRESSURE MAINTENANCE METHOD

Injection Pressure (Psia)	Production Wells	Injection Wells	NPV MM\$	IRR %	Gas Produced %	Oil Produced %
5535	3	2	665.2	156	68.18	66.81
6000	3	2	854.4	162	67.05	70.59
6300	3	2	853.7	164	68.18	71.43
6500	3	2	846.6	162	73.86	73.95
7000	3	2	829.9	164	92.61	81.09
8000	3	2	829.3	164	92.61	81.09

TABLE 4. FINAL RESULTS OF SIMULATION

Method	NPV MM\$	IRR %	Produced Gas %	Produced Oil %
Depletion	622.4	165	41.42	39.35
Partial Pressure Maintenance	865	162	85.23	77.73
Full Pressure Maintenance	854.4	162	67.05	70.59